

Online Supplementary Materials

Climate Resilience Investments and Agricultural Household Livelihoods:

Lessons from a Climate-Vulnerable Economy

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This online supplementary material provides additional methodological details, descriptive evidence, and robustness analyses that support the empirical results presented in the main text. Specifically, it summarizes key findings from the PPCR impact evaluation; describes the characteristics of the survey areas; documents the SWIFT methodology used to estimate household consumption expenditure; details the data collection process; and includes the survey questionnaire.

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A. Key Findings from the PPCR Impact Evaluation

The first two columns in each table report the means of the treatment and control groups of the major outcome variables. The difference between these means is statistically tested using a “difference-in-means” approach. The marginal effects are computed from linear probability regression models and refer to the difference between treatment and control areas, *ceteris paribus*. The causal effect of the PPCR projects is thus defined as the difference in outcomes between agricultural households located in PPCR grids and those in non-PPCR grids. The odd ratios are derived from logistic regression models. The 95% confidence intervals are reported for both marginal effects and odds ratio. The asterisks indicate the statistical significance levels of the marginal effects or odds ratios, using standard errors clustered at the district level to account for spatially correlated heterogeneity. The sample sizes of the treatment and control groups are reported in the last two columns of each table.

Table A1: PPCR impacts on household poverty

(%)	Mean _C	Mean _T	Diff	Marginal Effects	Odds Ratio	n _C	n _T
Household poverty incidence	0.820	0.869	0.049	0.026 *** [0.01,0.041]	1.525 *** [1.214,1.917]	963	964

Note: ***, **, and * indicate statistical significance at the 1, 5, and 10 percent critical levels, respectively.

Table A2: PPCR impacts on employment

(%)	Mean _C	Mean _T	Diff	Marginal Effects	Odds Ratio	n _C	n _T
Employment of labor force age 15-64	0.715	0.736	0.021	0.025 [-0.042,0.091]	1.160 [0.783,1.721]	1796	1802
Employment of labor force age 15-24	0.406	0.419	0.013	0.013 [-0.097,0.123]	1.057 [0.666,1.677]	468	470
Employment of labor force age 25-34	0.728	0.749	0.021	0.018 [-0.054,0.091]	1.114 [0.727,1.709]	518	533
Employment of labor force age 35-54	0.881	0.912	0.031	0.022 [-0.013,0.056]	1.370 [0.825,2.273]	679	651
Employment of labor force age 55-64	0.916	0.926	0.01	<0.001 [<0.001, <0.001]	1.611 [0.359,7.227]	131	148

Note: ***, **, and * indicate statistical significance at the 1, 5, and 10 percent critical levels, respectively.

Table A3: PPCR impacts on income diversifications

(%)	Mean _C	Mean _T	Diff	Marginal Effects	Odds Ratio	n _C	n _T
Employed workers age 15-64 with non-agricultural income	0.388	0.369	-0.019	0.008 [-0.084,0.101]	1.039 [0.686,1.574]	1285	1327
Households with more than 95% share of non-agricultural income	0.235	0.203	-0.032	0.025 [-0.027,0.076]	1.362 [0.672,2.759]	926	920
Households with non-agricultural income	0.477	0.472	-0.005	0.059 [-0.046,0.165]	1.269 [0.828,1.944]	926	920
Agricultural households with agricultural diversification	0.543	0.455	-0.088	-0.080 * [-0.175,0.014]	0.725 * [0.495,1.061]	484	486

Note: ***, **, and * indicate statistical significance at the 1, 5, and 10 percent critical levels, respectively.

Table A4: PPCR impacts on beneficiaries and adaptative strategies based on the PPCR projects

(%)	Mean _C	Mean _T	Diff	Marginal Effects	Odds Ratio	n _C	n _T
Are/Were you a beneficiary of the PPCR projects?	0.107	0.395	0.288**	0.278 *** [0.154,0.403]	5.770 *** [2.482,13.415]	807	849
Did you receive any benefits from the PPCR projects?	0.114	0.416	0.302**	0.296 *** [0.164,0.428]	5.877 *** [2.522,13.696]	807	849

ADAPTATIVE STRATEGIES BASED ON THE PPCR PROJECTS

Adaptation of crops and crop management

Encourage introduction of new crops that require less water	0.040	0.112	0.072***	0.058 *** [0.026,0.09]	2.983 *** [1.654,5.379]	807	849
Encourage introduction of new crops that are adapted to higher temperatures	0.035	0.087	0.052**	0.043 *** [0.012,0.073]	2.672 *** [1.384,5.16]	807	849

(%)	Mean _C	Mean _T	Diff	Marginal Effects		Odds Ratio		n _C	n _T
Encourage changes in sowing dates	0.029	0.064	0.035*	0.024 **	[0.005,0.042]	2.265 ***	[1.23,4.17]	807	849
Provide shade and drinking water for animals at pasture	0.033	0.153	0.120**	0.097 ***	[0.047,0.146]	4.997 ***	[1.975,12.64]	807	849
Develop breeds or change to breeds adapted to changed conditions, especially drought and heat resistant varieties	0.029	0.094	0.065***	0.058 ***	[0.02,0.095]	3.677 ***	[1.953,6.925]	807	849
Restoring natural features such as hedgerows to help reduce erosion	0.019	0.027	0.008	0.003	[-0.004,0.01]	1.370	[0.638,2.94]	807	849
Develop farming practices that minimize susceptibility to new pests and diseases	0.010	0.047	0.037**	0.027 **	[0.005,0.048]	4.817 ***	[2.014,11.522]	807	849
Increase ground cover, by changing field design e.g. to expanded field margins	0.011	0.032	0.021**	0.008 **	[0.001,0.014]	2.928 **	[1.149,7.461]	807	849
Enhancing the efficiency of fertilizer use	0.019	0.040	0.021**	0.013 *	[-0.001,0.027]	2.068 *	[0.971,4.407]	807	849
Developing land management practices to adapt to changes in soil properties	0.014	0.021	0.007	0.005	[-0.003,0.013]	1.687	[0.556,5.114]	807	849
Maximising effectiveness of labour and machinery	0.005	0.014	0.009	0.005	[-0.002,0.012]	3.092 *	[0.895,10.677]	807	849
Facilitate the transfer of technologies from relevant climatic zones	0.011	0.020	0.009	0.004	[-0.004,0.013]	1.772	[0.728,4.315]	807	849

(%)	Mean _C	Mean _T	Diff	Marginal Effects		Odds Ratio	n _C	n _T	
Adaptation of agricultural water management									
Adopt suitable upland farm or land management practices so that upland areas are used to slow run off and reduce peak water flows	0.012	0.031	0.019	0.016	[-0.004,0.035]	2.544	[0.714,9.062]	807	849
Adopt measures to reduce the impacts of extreme precipitation events	0.005	0.021	0.016***	0.012 ***	[0.003,0.022]	4.367 ***	[1.628,11.712]	807	849
Encourage introduction of new management techniques e.g. requiring less water	0.011	0.032	0.021	0.010 **	[0.002,0.017]	2.700 **	[1.031,7.075]	807	849
Introduce measures to secure safety of livestock during extreme flooding events	0.022	0.127	0.105**	0.079 ***	[0.041,0.117]	6.345 ***	[2.882,13.968]	807	849
Alter conservation practices for dry summers	0.010	0.026	0.016	0.010 *	[-0.002,0.022]	2.571 *	[0.971,6.803]	807	849
Adopt more effective use of irrigation	0.021	0.067	0.046*	0.031 ***	[0.016,0.046]	3.247 **	[1.126,9.358]	807	849
Increase in irrigation area and or water volume	0.016	0.072	0.056	0.037 ***	[0.018,0.055]	4.405 *	[0.964,20.139]	807	849
Adopt water re-use technology	0.014	0.081	0.067	0.036 ***	[0.019,0.053]	6.059 ***	[1.698,21.622]	807	849
Controlling, monitoring, and information systems									
Monitoring the changes on biodiversity that may occur due to changes in agricultural crops (for example, changes in rice fields modify the habitats of many bird species)	0.001	0.007	0.006**	0.002	[-0.002,0.006]	5.314	[0.645,43.805]	807	849

(%)	Mean _C	Mean _T	Diff	Marginal Effects		Odds Ratio		n _C	n _T
Monitoring new pests and diseases	0.010	0.053	0.043**	0.03 **	[0.005,0.055]	5.483 ***	[1.704,17.645]	807	849
Monitoring changes in soil properties	0.002	0.013	0.011**	0.002 **	[0,0.005]	4.941	[0.636,38.391]	807	849
Information systems to raise awareness of the changes and possible risks and opportunities	0.009	0.014	0.005	0.003	[-0.004,0.01]	1.559	[0.606,4.011]	807	849
Structural and financial adaptation									
Permanent changes in farm structure, such as buildings, irrigation systems, heating or cooling structure	0.014	0.022	0.008	0.004	[-0.008,0.016]	1.373	[0.465,4.061]	807	849
Establishing business plans with regular reviews to ensure effective responses to climatic events	0.007	0.039	0.032	0.015 ***	[0.004,0.026]	4.513 **	[1.321,15.415]	807	849
Planning for capital investment to adapt to climate change	0.009	0.066	0.057**	0.040 ***	[0.02,0.06]	7.603 ***	[2.29,25.243]	807	849
Development of a common strategy for adaptation to climate change between the farming sectors and the insurance community	0.002	0.025	0.023	0.010 ***	[0.004,0.016]	10.523 **	[1.746,63.424]	807	849

Note: ***, **, and * indicate statistical significance at the 1, 5, and 10 percent critical levels, respectively.

Table A5: PPCR impacts on adaptation of crops and crop management

(%)	Mean _C	Mean _T	Diff	Marginal Effects		Odds Ratio		n _C	n _T
Adaptation of crops and crop management (Any of adaptative strategies)	0.087	0.282	0.195***	0.195 ***	[0.085,0.305]	4.125 ***	[2.078,8.19]	807	849
Adaptation of crops and crop management (25% of adaptative strategies)	0.025	0.048	0.023	0.024	[-0.008,0.055]	1.997	[0.848,4.702]	807	849
Adaptation of crops and crop management (50% of adaptative strategies)	0.009	0.016	0.007	0.008	[-0.004,0.02]	1.916	[0.72,5.101]	807	849
Adaptation of agricultural water management (Any of adaptative strategies)	0.056	0.238	0.182**	0.182 **	[0.012,0.352]	5.287 ***	[1.826,15.307]	807	849
Adaptation of agricultural water management (25% of adaptative strategies)	0.012	0.054	0.042*	0.042 *	[-0.003,0.086]	4.566 ***	[1.597,13.049]	807	849
Adaptation of agricultural water management (50% of adaptative strategies)	0.004	0.015	0.011**	0.012 **	[0.001,0.022]	4.167 **	[1.29,13.465]	807	849
Controlling, monitoring, and information systems (Any of adaptative strategies)	0.017	0.065	0.048**	0.047 **	[0.009,0.086]	3.924 ***	[1.552,9.919]	807	849
Controlling, monitoring, and information systems (25% of adaptative strategies)	0.002	0.012	0.010**	0.009 **	[0.001,0.018]	4.797 **	[1.028,22.389]	807	849
Controlling, monitoring, and information systems (50% of adaptative strategies)	0.002	0.007	0.005	0.005	[-0.001,0.01]	2.865	[0.627,13.084]	807	849
Structural and financial adaptation (Any of adaptative strategies)	0.022	0.112	0.090*	0.090 *	[-0.003,0.182]	5.523 ***	[1.86,16.401]	807	849
Structural and financial adaptation (25% of adaptative strategies)	0.005	0.034	0.029*	0.029 *	[-0.002,0.061]	7.100 **	[1.521,33.135]	807	849

(%)	Mean _C	Mean _T	<i>Diff</i>	Marginal Effects		Odds Ratio	n _C	n _T	
Structural and financial adaptation (50% of adaptative strategies)	0.005	0.004	-0.001	-0.001	[-0.008,0.005]	0.712	[0.157,3.227]	807	849

Note: ***, **, and * indicate statistical significance at the 1, 5, and 10 percent critical levels, respectively.

B. Descriptive Characteristics of Survey Areas

	ALL	PPCR grids	Non-PPCR grids	PPCR beneficiaries	Non-PPCR beneficiaries
Number of sample households	1,927	988	939	465	1,462
Number of sample individuals	10,417	5,227	5,190	2,626	7,791
Total weight of households (thousands)	406	213	192	26	380
Total weight of individuals (thousands)	2,120	1,106	1,013	166	1,953
BASIC INFORMATION					
Poverty incidence (% of households)	71	62	81	76	71
Average household size	5.2	5.2	5.3	6.4	5.1
Population size					
Females (%)	56%	56%	56%	56%	56%
Ratio of household members aged 0-4	12%	12%	12%	12%	12%
Ratio of household members aged 0-14	42%	40%	44%	48%	41%
Ratio of household members aged 15-64	55%	57%	52%	51%	55%
Ratio of household members aged 65+	3%	3%	4%	1%	4%
Dependency ratio	82%	74%	91%	96%	81%
Average age	23	23	22	22	23
Literate Males (%)	79%	81%	77%	75%	79%
Literate Females (%)	77%	68%	69%	64%	75%
<i>Males</i>					
None	9%	6%	13%	8%	9%
Below primary	24%	24%	24%	24%	24%
Primary	28%	28%	29%	32%	28%
Lower Secondary	19%	18%	19%	13%	19%
Upper Secondary	15%	18%	12%	16%	15%
Bachelor or Higher	5%	6%	3%	6%	4%
<i>Females</i>					

	ALL	PPCR grids	Non-PPCR grids	PPCR beneficiaries	Non-PPCR beneficiaries
None	11%	6%	13%	12%	11%
Below primary	24%	24%	24%	31%	24%
Primary	28%	28%	29%	29%	28%
Lower Secondary	18%	18%	19%	14%	18%
Upper Secondary	13%	18%	12%	13%	13%
Bachelor or Higher	5%	6%	3%	0%	6%
Studying, if age<18 (%)	62%	63%	60%	68%	61%
Working, if age 15+ (%)	57%	51%	65%	65%	57%
Head of household: Age	44	42	46	49	44
Head of household: Female (%)	35%	28%	43%	21%	36%
Head of household: Years of schooling	10.59	10.88	10.23	10.56	10.59
Head of household: Active in labor market	92%	90%	93%	86%	92%
Head of household: Agricultural sector	50%	33%	68%	58%	49%
Ratio of employer	2%	3%	0%	0%	2%
Ratio of own-account worker	65%	46%	81%	76%	64%
Ratio of unpaid family worker	1%	0%	1%	0%	1%
Ratio of private employee	16%	30%	5%	8%	17%
Ratio of public employee	16%	19%	13%	15%	16%
DWELLING CHARACTERISTICS AND ASSETS					
Housing: traditional or improved traditional housing/mix	46%	22%	73%	66%	45%
Housing: flat/apartment/multi-unit	5%	7%	3%	0%	6%
Roof: thatch/plam/wood/grass/straw	25%	5%	47%	36%	24%
Roof: metal/iron sheets	69%	90%	47%	63%	70%
Wall: burnt pan bricks	30%	49%	9%	17%	31%
Wall: mud	23%	9%	39%	48%	22%
Wall: cement	27%	31%	23%	17%	28%
Wall: pole/dagga/mud	14%	5%	23%	16%	13%

	ALL	PPCR grids	Non-PPCR grids	PPCR beneficiaries	Non-PPCR beneficiaries
Wall: grass	3%	1%	6%	2%	3%
Floor: concrete	58%	80%	33%	38%	59%
Floor: mud	32%	16%	50%	53%	31%
Floor: wood	0%	0%	1%	0%	0%
Number of rooms	3.0	3.3	2.7	2.8	3.0
Light: electricity	23%	39%	5%	22%	23%
Light: solar panel	24%	24%	25%	15%	25%
Light: candle	2%	3%	1%	2%	2%
Light: none	1%	0%	2%	1%	1%
Cooking: wood	60%	43%	79%	76%	59%
Cooking: charcoal	30%	39%	19%	17%	31%
Cooking: electricity	9%	17%	1%	0%	10%
Garbage: collected	1%	2%	0%	0%	1%
Garbage: burnt	5%	3%	7%	3%	5%
Garbage: dumping	29%	29%	28%	27%	29%
Garbage: pit	65%	65%	64%	71%	64%
Toilet: flush	11%	19%	3%	15%	11%
Toilet: latrine	78%	75%	80%	64%	78%
Toilet: none	6%	3%	10%	16%	5%
Assets: radio	45%	52%	36%	34%	45%
Assets: tv	40%	53%	25%	32%	40%
Assets: refrigerator/freezer	18%	30%	5%	22%	18%
Assets: land phone	1%	1%	2%	0%	1%
Assets: bicycle	29%	34%	23%	22%	29%
Assets: motor vehicles	9%	15%	3%	23%	8%
Assets: computer and laptop	10%	13%	7%	2%	11%
Assets: motorcycles	2%	2%	1%	2%	2%

	ALL	PPCR grids	Non-PPCR grids	PPCR beneficiaries	Non-PPCR beneficiaries
Assets: plough	12%	12%	11%	12%	12%
Assets: scotch cart	5%	6%	3%	6%	5%
Assets: mobile phone	73%	86%	59%	76%	73%
Assets: oxen	8%	13%	3%	15%	8%
Assets: wheelbarrow	9%	11%	6%	14%	8%
AGRICULTURE					
Ratio of agricultural households	78%	70%	87%	99%	77%
Share of income from agriculture to total household income	56%	29%	83%	60%	56%
Share of income to total agricultural income					
from crops	65%	54%	75%	72%	65%
from poultry	18%	25%	13%	12%	19%
from livestock	11%	15%	7%	12%	11%
from fish	4%	6%	2%	2%	4%
from other farming	2%	0%	3%	1%	2%
Percentage of agricultural households producing following crop:					
Local maize	51%	24%	74%	48%	51%
Hybrid maize	30%	36%	25%	33%	30%
Cassava	27%	1%	49%	38%	26%
Mixed beans	15%	5%	23%	8%	15%
Sweet potatoes	16%	8%	23%	7%	17%
Groundnuts	19%	16%	21%	21%	19%
Vegetables	9%	7%	11%	5%	9%
Activities					
1 agricultural activity	34%	45%	24%	40%	33%
2 agricultural activities	37%	33%	40%	26%	38%
3 and more than 3 agricultural activities	29%	22%	36%	33%	29%
Farm type					

	ALL	PPCR grids	Non-PPCR grids	PPCR beneficiaries	Non-PPCR beneficiaries
Crop production only	22%	22%	22%	25%	22%
Non-crop production only	18%	36%	2%	16%	18%
Mix production	60%	43%	76%	59%	60%
Facilities					
Access to food market	74%	97%	47%	90%	73%
Distance to food market (km)	5.6	5.5	5.8	7.5	5.4
Access to hammer mill	96%	97%	95%	98%	96%
Distance to hammer mill (km)	4.5	1.5	8.3	50.4	1.2
Access to input market	54%	70%	36%	75%	52%
Distance to input market (km)	9.2	9.2	9.4	8.1	9.3
Access to internet café	19%	27%	10%	2%	20%
Distance to internet café (km)	13.3	12.0	19.9	9.8	13.4
Access to bank	30%	46%	12%	38%	29%
Distance to bank (km)	17.2	16.1	22.5	9.8	17.6
Climate Change - Self Reported					
Flood incidence reported during last 12 months	46%	34%	58%	59%	45%
Floods are more frequent in the past 5 years compared to past	44%	36%	51%	47%	44%
Floods are more severe in the past 5 years compared to past	37%	24%	50%	34%	38%
Drought incidence reported during last 12 months	67%	71%	63%	73%	67%
Droughts are more frequent in the past 5 years compared to past	72%	83%	60%	50%	74%
Droughts are more severe in the past 5 years compared to past	69%	81%	55%	38%	72%
Impact of shocks (above average)					
Economic impact	46%	41%	51%	45%	46%
Ability (to earn income) impact	34%	36%	32%	26%	35%
Crop production impact	48%	41%	56%	45%	48%
Livestock production impact	24%	19%	28%	32%	23%
Farmland impact	15%	11%	19%	22%	15%

	ALL	PPCR grids	Non-PPCR grids	PPCR beneficiaries	Non-PPCR beneficiaries
Food shortage	39%	22%	57%	59%	37%
Importance of adaptations					
Use of drought tolerant varieties	69%	84%	54%	60%	70%
Practicing crop diversification	78%	84%	73%	77%	78%
Integrated farming system	63%	72%	55%	63%	63%
Increased use of irrigation	67%	75%	59%	61%	67%
Practicing crop rotation	80%	89%	71%	77%	80%
Importance of constraints					
Lack of available water (both irrigation and drinking)	70%	81%	60%	50%	72%
Unpredicted weather	83%	93%	75%	80%	84%
Lack of credit/money	85%	89%	81%	81%	85%
Lack of market access	85%	84%	87%	94%	84%
Shortage of farm inputs	80%	80%	80%	80%	80%
Lack of information	87%	92%	81%	68%	89%
Ability to take precautions/prepared	18%	15%	22%	35%	17%
Precautions used against shocks					
Plant different crops	46%	35%	58%	62%	45%
Store dry food	54%	51%	57%	70%	53%
Mitigations you think can improve negative effect of risks					
Financial support	77%	81%	73%	88%	76%
Access to information	83%	83%	82%	70%	83%
Improved road access	75%	78%	71%	84%	74%
Methods used to improve farming					
Fertiliser or manure	39%	36%	41%	39%	39%
Different crop varieties	28%	29%	28%	25%	28%
Early maturing varieties	27%	35%	19%	21%	28%
Information received					

	ALL	PPCR grids	Non-PPCR grids	PPCR beneficiaries	Non-PPCR beneficiaries
Radio broadcasts about climate/weather	66%	67%	65%	84%	65%
Text (SMS) messages about climate/weather	38%	40%	35%	50%	37%
Television updates about climate/weather	40%	54%	23%	30%	40%
PPCR project					
PPCR beneficiary	6%	5%	8%	100%	0%
Do you know the location of any PPCR projects?					
In ward	20%	21%	20%	69%	17%
In district	21%	24%	17%	50%	19%
In province	12%	22%	1%	3%	13%
Received benefits from what type of projects					
Crop production	1%	1%	1%	14%	0%
Livestock	1%	1%	2%	18%	0%
Construction of water resource supply	4%	4%	3%	50%	1%
Encouraged adaptative strategies					
Adaptation of crops and crop management	6%	4%	8%	89%	0%
Adaptation of agricultural water management	3%	3%	2%	40%	0%
Structural and financial adaptation	1%	2%	1%	18%	0%
Development					
Provision of Mobile Phone Network?	37%	39%	35%	54%	36%
Provision of Harmermill?	21%	25%	18%	30%	21%
Agricultural Inputs provision?	17%	21%	12%	51%	14%
Transport Services Provided or Improved?	24%	38%	9%	31%	24%

Note: All calculations apply sampling weights to be representative of the statistical population.

C. SWIFT methodology for estimating household consumption expenditure

SWIFT (Survey of Well-being via Instant, Frequent Tracking) is a rapid poverty assessment tool developed in-house by the World Bank's Poverty and Equity Global Practice. It enables the timely, cost-effective, and user-friendly production of accurate household consumption expenditure and poverty estimates and has been used to improve the availability and frequency of official poverty statistics.

SWIFT builds on traditional household socio-economic (SES) data by first training its models on full household consumption or income surveys, where poverty is measured using standard welfare aggregates. From these surveys, a parsimonious set of SES variables—such as education, employment, household composition, asset ownership, and housing characteristics—is selected based on their strong correlation with consumption or income. These reduced SES indicators are then used in short surveys to predict household welfare, allowing poverty and inequality to be monitored frequently without repeatedly collecting detailed consumption data.

Basics and Assumptions

Compared with a typical household consumption data collection, SWIFT is much faster and more cost-effective for producing consumption or income data and poverty statistics. Instead of collecting detailed household consumption or income data, SWIFT collects only 10 to 30 questions on poverty-correlated variables and projects household income or expenditure from them using a custom-built model, from which poverty and inequality statistics are estimated. These poverty correlates typically include household size, household head's educational attainment and employment status, ownership of consumer durables and housing conditions. Collecting responses to the selected questions usually takes only 7 to 10 minutes per household, compared with at least one hour for a standard household consumption or income survey. Moreover, poverty and inequality statistics can be estimated from the SWIFT data in one minute or less.

The development of a consumption or income model is critical for SWIFT, as the reliability of poverty estimates depends heavily on how accurately the model can project household expenditure or income. In building the model, we assume linearity in coefficients between household income or expenditure and poverty correlates, with an associated projection error. In building the model, we assume linearity in coefficients between household income or

expenditure and poverty correlates, with an associated projection error.⁴ This relationship is formally expressed in equation (1):

$$\ln y_h = x_h' \beta + u_h \quad (1)$$

where $\ln y_h$ denotes the natural logarithm of household income or expenditure for household h , x_h is a $(k \times 1)$ vector of poverty correlates of household h , β is a $(k \times 1)$ vector of coefficients, k is the number of variables, and u_h is the projection error. A SWIFT survey collects information on poverty correlates. To improve projection accuracy, SWIFT adopts approaches from machine learning, poverty mapping, and multiple imputations. More details are available in annex and the guideline for SWIFT (Yoshida, et al., 2015).⁵

The regression model yields a formula that is used to project household income or expenditure in a dataset containing only poverty correlates. The latter dataset is collected through a SWIFT survey.

The SWIFT modeling process involves multiple steps to enhance the model's ability to project household income or expenditures. This is achieved by estimating model coefficients (β) and the associated distributions of both the coefficients and the projection errors. Because no predictive model is exact, explicitly accounting for the projection errors is essential. In fact, estimating the distribution of the projection errors is critical for producing reliable poverty estimates and their corresponding standard errors.

Cross Validation

Since consumption patterns can differ significantly across areas and population groups, the SWIFT team makes efforts to create a model that is specific to the areas and population groups of interest. While such an adjustment helps create a model tailored to specific needs, it may introduce substantial bias in poverty estimates because the sample used to construct the model becomes smaller when focusing on a specific population group. Overfitting is one of such problems. The overfitting problem means that while a model can perform well within the sample developed for the model, it can perform badly outside the dataset. In a sense, the model overfits the dataset used to develop it. To detect the problem the SWIFT team conducts a cross-

⁴ This does not mean SWIFT does not use non-linear models; rather, it means that SWIFT's formula is linear in the variables constructed in the dataset. Since some variables can be squares of other variables, the resulting formula can be non-linear. One of typical examples is the inclusion of household size and household size squared in the model.

⁵ Yoshida, N., R. Munoz, A. Skinner, C. Kyung-eun Lee, M. Brataj, W. Durbin, D. Sharma, and C. Wieser. (2015). SWIFT Data Collection Guidelines version 2. The World Bank.

validation analysis. The cross-validation approach separates data used for developing the model from those used for evaluating the model fitness.

More specifically, a household survey dataset is split randomly into 10 subsamples. Each of these subsamples is called a “fold.” A consumption model is estimated from nine folds by running a stepwise Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression.⁶ The stepwise OLS regression means that a statistical package searches for an OLS regression model where all variables are statistically significant, at a given p-value level. We use Stata and its stepwise selection model. The nine folds used for developing a model are known as “training data”.

After a model is selected, household expenditure or income data is projected using the model in the remaining fold, and a poverty rate and mean squared errors (MSEs) are estimated with the projected data. At the cross-validation stage, we project household expenditure or income data, assuming the error term and regression coefficients follow normal distributions.

More specifically, suppose $\hat{\beta}$ is a vector of estimated coefficients and $\hat{\sigma}^2$ is an OLS estimator of error variance. We first draw a random value χ from a chi distribution with a degree of freedom, $(N - k)$, where N refers to the total sample size and k refers to the number of variables selected by the stepwise regression procedure, and calculate $\tilde{\sigma} = \hat{\sigma}(N - k)/\chi$. We then draw $\tilde{\beta}$ from a normal distribution of $(\hat{\beta}, \tilde{\sigma}(X'X)^{-1})$ where X is a $(N \times k)$ matrix of $(x_1, \dots, x_h, \dots, x_N)'$. Finally, we draw a simulated household expenditure or income for household h , $\widetilde{\ln y}_h$, from a normal distribution of $(X\hat{\beta}, \tilde{\sigma}I_{N \times N})$ where $I_{N \times N}$ refers to an $(N \times N)$ identity matrix. This simulation process is repeated for all households, typically twenty times.⁷ A poverty headcount rate is calculated by comparing the simulated household expenditure or income with a poverty line for each of the twenty simulation rounds. The average poverty rate of the simulations is used as a poverty estimate. MSE is calculated in the testing data by taking the average of the sum of squared differences between y_h and $\hat{y}_h = x'_h * \hat{\beta}$.

This analysis is repeated 10 times, each of which uses a different fold as testing data to test the performance in terms of mean squared errors and the absolute value of the difference between the projected and actual poverty rates. This test detects the over-fitting problem because all testing statistics are calculated from out-of-sample.

Figure C1 shows an illustration of a three-fold cross validation exercise.

⁶ Alternatively, weighted least squares.

⁷ This process can be done using STATA's command “mi impute regress”, or STATA Corp LP (2013).

Figure C1 Illustration of 3-Fold Cross-Validation

Step 1: Randomly split data into three folds (C refers to consumption; X refers to non-consumption data)

Step 2: Select two folds as training data, develop a model there, and test model performance in the testing data

Step 3: Repeat the above procedure three times by changing the testing data

This cross-validation exercise is conducted to determine the optimal threshold of the p-value for the stepwise regressions. For a specific p-value, the cross-validation exercise is done and produces two testing statistics. The exercise is repeated for different levels of p-value, usually between 0.1% and 10%. The optimal p-value is the value where the absolute value of the difference between the actual and the projected poverty rates is minimized. The mean squared error is also examined to check whether the over-fitting problem occurs. If the mean squared error is minimized at a level of p that is smaller than the value where the absolute difference between the actual and the projected poverty rates is minimized, then the former value is chosen as the optimal threshold.

Finalizing the Model

After the optimal p-value is selected, a stepwise OLS regression procedure is carried out with a full sample of data to estimate a model. To ensure that the coefficients are stable, an OLS regression with the set of variables is carried out for all ten testing datasets to see whether the coefficients of the select variables do not change signs or are dropped due to collinearity. If some variables are dropped due to collinearity or some signs of the coefficients change, then these variables will be dropped from the final model. After dropping these variables, an OLS regression is carried out to estimate the coefficients and variance of the coefficients and error terms.

Simulation and Estimation of Poverty Rates

The final model is used to project household expenditure or income for all households 20 times following the procedure presented above. Poverty rates are estimated for each round of simulation, and the average is taken as the estimate of the poverty rate. The variance of the poverty estimate is calculated using the following formula (Rubin, 1987; Schafer, 1999):

$$V(H^*) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{m}\right) \left[\left(\frac{1}{m-1}\right) (\sum_{l=1}^m (H^l - H^*)^2)\right] + \left[\frac{1}{m} \sum_{l=1}^m V(H^l)\right] \quad (\text{a.2})$$

where m refers to the number of simulations, H^l refers to the poverty estimate in round l of the simulation, H^* refers to a mean of $\{H^l\}$ and the final estimate of the poverty headcount rate, and $V(H^l)$ is an estimate of the variance of the poverty estimate in round l of simulation. The first bracket presents the between-simulation variance, while the second squared bracket presents the within-simulation variance. Consequently, the variance of the final poverty estimate is a weighted average of the within and between simulation variances.

D. Data collection

Box C1: Brief of Sample

Sampling Method:	Grid Based Stratified Sampling
Stratification variables:	Project area and province
Primary Sampling Unit:	Grid
Secondary Sampling Unit:	Household
Target Population:	Western and Southern provinces
Sample Selection Method:	PPS Random Sampling (Probability to Proportionate to Size)

Sampling Frame

The sampling frame is a list of all units of analysis within a population. In the Zambian survey, the sample frame is all households (unit of analysis) within the population (all eligible households in Western and Southern Provinces)

In most countries, a household sample frame as described above is not available. While an ideal sample frame is not accessible, accurate household counts must be available to calculate probabilities of selection which would refer to a household's power of representation.

In the Zambian case, grid-based sampling was adopted to overcome the problems of a sampling frame where the number of households were estimated for each grid by Global Human Settlement Layers (GHSL). By using the grid-based approach, selection probabilities of households can be calculated.

There is a total of 575,490 households in the Southern and Western Provinces. Of these, 37,825 reside in the project area.

Stratification of the Sampling Frame

Stratifying a sample frame is done to create homogenous units among strata. When stratified properly, we expect the unit of analysis within a stratum to be somewhat similar. In the Zambian survey, considering the needs and scope of the study, province and project area status were considered as stratification variables.

Table C1 Stratification matrix

	Southern	Western
PPCR grids	X	x
Non-PPCR grids	X	x

Table C2 Total number of households living in and outside of the project area

	Southern	Western	TOTAL
PPCR grids	4,110	33,715	37,825
Non-PPCR grids	359,714	177,951	537,665
TOTAL	363,824	211,666	575,490

Table C3 Population distribution of households living in the project area

	Southern	Western	TOTAL
PPCR grids	11%	89%	100%
Non-PPCR grids	67%	33%	100%
TOTAL	63%	37%	100%

Cluster Size

For this survey, cluster size—the number of sample households from each grid—was 15. Moreover, in this study, each grid size was 1 km × 1 km.

Sample Size Calculation

The survey sample size was calculated separately for PPCR project area coverage. The total sample size is estimated to be 1,800 households, of which 781 were from PPCR project area and 1,019 from non-project area. During the sample size calculation, based on available previous survey estimates, it was estimated that the margin of error of PPCR project area would be around 3.5% while for non-project area it would be around 3.3%.

The margin of error is used to calculate the sample size. The formula was used for the estimation of margin of error for binary parameters.

$$\text{Margin of Error (ME)} = z_{\alpha}^2 \sqrt{\frac{\hat{p}(1 - \hat{p})}{n}}$$

Desired Margin of Error = 3.5%

\hat{p} = our prior judgment of the correct value of p . We accept $p = 0.5$ as there is no prior information to maximize variance.

$z_{\alpha}^2 = 1.96$ for a 95% confidence interval

n = sample size

Sample Size Formula

When interest is in a population proportion (i.e. the primary outcome variable is categorical—specifically, binary), the total number of subjects required (N) is:

$$N = Z_{\alpha}^2 \frac{p(1-p)}{\text{Margin of Error}^2} (\text{Def}f)(\text{Non-response})$$

where p is the expected proportion who have the characteristic of interest, and z_{α} is a value from the normal distribution related to and representing the confidence level (equal to 1.96 for 95% confidence). The design effect (*Def*f) adjusts the required sample size to account for the loss of statistical efficiency arising from cluster or grid-based sampling rather than simple random sampling. The non-response (*Non-response*) factor inflates the sample size to ensure sufficient observations remain after accounting for households that do not participate in the survey.

When interest is in a population mean (i.e. the primary outcome variable is continuous), the total number of subjects required (N) is:

$$N = Z_{\alpha}^2 \frac{\text{Standard Deviation}^2}{\text{Margin of Error}^2} (\text{Def}f)(\text{Non-response})$$

where z_{α} is a value from the normal distribution related to and representing the confidence level (equal to 1.96 for 95% confidence).

Sample Allocation

This study adopts proportional allocation techniques to allocate samples across strata. The table below presents the allocation of sample size for each Stratum. Sample size is calculated by using “Proportion to Stratum Size” methodology.

Table C4 Allocation of the estimated sample size for project and non-project area

	Southern	Western	TOTAL
PPCR grids	85	696	781
Non-PPCR grids	682	337	1,019
TOTAL	767	1,033	1,800

There is a total of 9,206 grids in the Southern and Western Provinces. Of these, 4,977 are in the project area.

Table C5 Sampling frame (grids)

	Number of Populated Grids in Project Area	Number of Populated Grids in Non-Project Area	Total Populated Grids
Southern	78	4,899	4,977
Western	1,197	3,032	4,229
TOTAL	1,275	7,931	9,206

The total number of sample grids was indicated in below table.

Table C6 Number of sample grids to be selected

Province	Number of Populated Grids in Project Area	Number of Populated Grids in Non-Project Area	Total Populated Grids
Southern	32	32	64
Western	32	32	64
TOTAL	64	64	128

Sample Selection Procedures

The sample selection methodology for the survey is based on a stratified multi-stage sample design. First areas, known as Primary Sampling Units (PSU) or Grid Segments, are selected according to the specified stratification and allocation. Secondly, dwellings were randomly selected according to specifications from the Grid Segment by using satellite images. Finally, where more than one household resides in a dwelling, all households were listed, and one household was randomly selected from each dwelling. Households were then listed, and sample households were randomly selected from each grid using satellite images.

Calculation of Sample Design Weights (Population Estimations)

Due to complex sample design, to obtain representative survey estimates, weights must be applied during analysis. These weights are required because the design is not an equal probability selection method; different sampling units were selected with different probabilities. Weights are used to allow the units to represent their share of population.

Design weights were calculated for households. The design weight is the inverse of the overall probability of selection of the unit. The design weight, d_{hi} for grid i in the h^{th} stratum is the reciprocal of the sampling fraction employed in calculating the number of units in that grid:

$$d_{hi} = \frac{1}{P_{hi}}$$

The term P_{hi} , the sampling fraction of households in the grid i in the h^{th} stratum, is the product of probabilities of selection at every stage for the households in this grid:

- **Weight for Grids:** Selection probability of the selected grid in each stratum
- **Weight for households:** Selection probability of each selected household within the selected Dwelling Units.

Therefore,

$$P_{hi} = P_1 \times P_2$$

where P_1 is the probability of selecting the i^{th} grid in the stratum h in the first stage of selection, and P_2 is the probability of sampling household in the same grid.

Post Stratification/Calibration

In some surveys, as in this study, some households may be over-sampled or under-sampled either accidentally or intentionally. In other words, the way a certain characteristic (such as regional distribution, housing types etc.) of the sample is distributed may differ from the way it is distributed in the population. This introduces bias into any estimate we may obtain from the sample data because statistical procedures will give greater weight to those people we over-sampled. We can correct for these biases mathematically with a post-stratification survey weight.

In order to calculate a post-stratification weight, we need an auxiliary data set to which to compare the sample data. For example, we would need census data or Current Population

Survey data that show the demographic characteristics of the population of Zambia. The GIS files from GHSL include number of households over stratum and this information were used as an auxiliary data.

Figure C1 Locations of selected grids

Figure C2 Locations of population households in a grid example

GRID ID: 477 **Western Province Mongu District**
STRATUM: W-Control **Kambule Ward**

**EXPLORING METHODOLOGIES TO MEASURE HOUSEHOLD
CLIMATE RESILIENCE IN VULNERABLE COUNTRIES AND
COMMUNITIES**

P160194

**HOUSEHOLD QUESTIONNAIRE
SOCIOECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS,
AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION,
AND CLIMATE RESILIENCE**

April 3, 2018

Section 1	A	Household identification particulars
Section 2	B	Household roster – for all persons
Section 3	C	Education – for all persons
Section 4	D	Economic activity – for all persons aged 5 years and above
Section 5	E	Household income from agricultural activity
Section 6	F	Individual income from non-agricultural activity – for all persons aged 5 years and above
Section 7	G	Household assets
Section 8	H	Agricultural production
Section 9	I	Climate resilience
Section 10	J	PPCR projects
Section 11	K	Household access to facilities
Section 12	L	Developmental issues

CONSENT FORM

"Hello! My name is: [.] , a research staff at [.] . We work with the World Bank conducting research on climate resilience in Zambia. We need your help so we can know more about your situation regarding agricultural production, impacts from climate risk and your climate resilience. You do not have to worry because all your answers will be private and confidential without anyone knowing about it. We request you to provide us true information as this is crucial, contributing to the climate resilience in vulnerable communities of Zambia, particularly the improvement of agriculture and welfare in your village.

At any point, you have the right to stop the interview, or you can ask any question you do not understand any time. The interview may take 1 hour. I stress that this is not a test or exam and there are no right or wrong answers, so please give true and honest answers.

If you have questions related to this study, please contact [.] Phone: [.] .

Do you have a question you want to ask me?

Do you agree to participate in this study?

1=Yes

2=No

SECTION A: HOUSEHOLD IDENTIFICATION PARTICULARS

ENUMERATOR/SUPERVISOR	CODE NUMBER
Enumerator's name	text only
1. Province name	text only
2. District name	text only
3. Ward name	text only
4. Select grid	Integer
5. Select point	Integer
Type of point ID	Integer
Original	1
Replaced	2
<i>If Type of Point ID = 1</i>	
Information about this point:	
Building/dwelling is residential, and I continue survey.	1
Building/dwelling is not for residential purpose (business office, shop, etc)	2
There is no one living at the selected building/dwelling at the time of survey	3
There is no one eligible/suitable to take part in the interview in this dwelling at the time of interview	4
Abandoned/demolished building/dwelling	5
Take a photo of dwelling	
GPS	
<i>make GPS check off-line feasible (by device and protocol)</i>	
HOUSEHOLD RESPONDENT	
6. Village or Locality Name	text only
A2. Name of Main Respondent	text only
A3. Total number of persons who live in this household	Max 2 digits
(Include Usual Members Absent) Definition of household: A usual member of a household is considered to be one who had been living with a household for at least six months prior to the survey. * Newly married couples were regarded as usual members of the household even if one or both had been in the household for less than six months. * The newly born babies of usual members were also considered as usual members of the household. * Members of the household who were at boarding schools or temporarily away from the household, e.g. away on seasonal work, in hospital, visiting relatives or friends, but who normally live and eat together, were included in the list of usual members of the household.	

SECTION B: HOUSEHOLD ROSTER – FOR ALL PERSONS

INTRODUCTION: I would like to start the interview by asking you questions about yourself and other usual members of the household (ask ALL questions)

QUESTIONS	CODE NUMBER
Serial number of household members (PID)	2 digits
B3. Full name	
B4. What is the year and month of birth of [NAME]? <i>Enter approximate Birth Year if unknown</i>	YEAR/MONTH
B5. What is the relationship of [Name] to the head of household?	2 digits
Head	1
Spouse	2
Own Child	3
Stepchild	4
Adopted Child	5
Grand Child	6
Brother/Sister	7
Cousin	8
Niece/Nephew	9
Brother/Sister-in Law	10
Parent	11
Parent-in-Law	12
Other Relative	13
Maid/Nanny/House-Servant	14
Other Non-relative	15
<i>Ask if Age is 14 Years or Above</i>	
B5a. Are you sure that [Name] - [age] years old, is the head of this household?	
B6. What is [Name]'s gender?	1 digit
Male	1
Female	2
<i>Ask if Age is 12 Years or Above</i>	
B7. What is the marital status of [Name] (for those aged 12 years and above only)?	1 digit
Never Married	1
Married	2
Separated	3
Divorced	4
Widowed	5
Co-habiting	6
B8. What languages does [Household head] speak? (starting with the language they speak most frequently at home)	1ST, 2ND, 3RD

English	1
Bemba	2
Kaonde	3
Koma	4
Lozi	5
Luchazi	6
Lunda	7
Luvale	8
Mbunda	9
Nkoya	10
Nyanja	11
Nyengo	12
Toka-Leya	13
Tonga	14
Others (specify)	98
B8a. The most frequently spoken language at home	
English	1
Bemba	2
Kaonde	3
Koma	4
Lozi	5
Luchazi	6
Lunda	7
Luvale	8
Mbunda	9
Nkoya	10
Nyanja	11
Nyengo	12
Toka-Leya	13
Tonga	14
Others (specify)	98
B8b. The second most frequently spoken language at home	
English	1
Bemba	2
Kaonde	3
Koma	4
Lozi	5
Luchazi	6
Lunda	7
Luvale	8
Mbunda	9

Nkoya	10
Nyanja	11
Nyengo	12
Toka-Leya	13
Tonga	14
Others (specify)	98
B8c. The third most frequently spoken language at home	
English	1
Bemba	2
Kaonde	3
Koma	4
Lozi	5
Luchazi	6
Lunda	7
Luvale	8
Mbunda	9
Nkoya	10
Nyanja	11
Nyengo	12
Toka-Leya	13
Tonga	14
Others (specify)	98

SECTION C: EDUCATION – FOR ALL PERSONS

INTRODUCTION: I am now going to ask you about the educational status of ALL members of this household (ask ALL questions)

QUESTIONS	CODE NUMBER
<i>Ask if Age is 5 Years or Above</i>	
C1. Has [Name] ever attended school?	1 digit
Yes	1
No [Skip to C5]	2
C2. Is [Name] currently attending school? [Ask if age is 5 Years or above]	1 digit
Yes	1
No	2
<i>Ask if age is 5 years or above</i>	
C3. What grade was [Name] attending last year?	2 digits
Pre-school	1
Grade 1	2
Grade 2	3
Grade 3	4
Grade 4	5
Grade 5	6
Grade 6	7
Grade 7	8
Grade 8	9
Grade 9	10
Grade 10	11
Grade 11	12
Grade 12 GCE (O-Level)	13
Grade 12 GCE (A-Level)	14
College students	15
Undergraduate university students	16
Post-graduate certificate/Diploma students	17
Master's degree students	18
Doctoral level or above students	19
Not attending	20
<i>If Answer 'No' for Question 2</i>	
C4. What was the Highest Grade / Level of Education [Name] Attended?	2 digits
Pre-school	1
Grade 1	2
Grade 2	3
Grade 3	4
Grade 4	5

Grade 5	6
Grade 6	7
Grade 7	8
Grade 8	9
Grade 9	10
Grade 10	11
Grade 11	12
Grade 12 GCE (O-Level)	13
Grade 12 GCE (A-Level)	14
College students	15
Undergraduate university students	16
Post-graduate certificate/Diploma students	17
Master's degree students	18
Doctoral level or above students	19
<i>Skip if C1 = 1 or C3 >= 5 or C4 >= 5</i>	
5. Read and write with understanding in any language?	1 digit
Can read	1
Can read and write	2
Cannot read or write	3

SECTION E: HOUSEHOLD INCOME FROM AGRICULTURAL ACTIVITY

INTRODUCTION: I am now going to ask you about the household income from agricultural activity

QUESTIONS	CODE NUMBER	E1av. WHAT WAS THE INCOME FROM SALES OR VALUE OF CONSUMPTION FROM HOUSEHOLD AGRICULTURAL ACTIVITY IN THE LAST 12 MONTHS (IN KWACHA)
E1. DID YOUR HOUSEHOLD GROW ANY CROPS IN THE LAST 12 MONTHS?	YES/NO	
CROPS		
1. Hybrid maize		
2. Local maize		
3. Cassava		
4. Groundnuts		
5. Rice		
6. Millet		
7. Sorghum		
8. Beans		
9. Soya beans		
10. Sweet potatoes		
11. Irish potatoes		
12. Vegetables		
13. Impwa		
14. Eggplant		
15. Okra		
16. Cotton		
17. Tobacco		
18. Sunflower		
19. Paprika		
20. Other crops (specify)		
E2a. DID YOUR HOUSEHOLD BREED ANY LIVESTOCK IN THE LAST 12 MONTHS? If so, tick the below options that adequately suit your pattern/purpose of breeding	YES/NO	E2. WHAT WAS THE INCOME FROM SALES OR VALUE OF CONSUMPTION FROM LIVESTOCK IN THE LAST 12 MONTHS (IN KWACHA)
LIVESTOCK		
1. Sale of own cattle (live)		
2. Sale of own cattle (slaughtered)		
3. Own cattle consumed		
4. Sale of own goats (live)		
5. Sale of own goats (slaughtered)		

6. Own goats consumed		
7. Sale of own sheep (live)		
8. Sale of own sheep (slaughtered)		
9. Own sheep consumed		
10. Sale of own pigs (live)		
11. Sale of own pigs (slaughtered)		
12. Own pigs consumed		
13. Sale of own produced livestock products such as milk, yoghurt, fat, cheese and hides, in the last 12 months?		
E3a. DID YOUR HOUSEHOLD OWN ANY POULTRY IN THE LAST 12 MONTHS? If so, tick the below options that adequately suit your pattern/purpose of ownership.	YES/NO	WHAT WAS THE INCOME FROM SALES OR VALUE OF CONSUMPTION FROM POULTRY IN THE LAST 12 MONTHS (IN KWACHA)
POULTRY		
1. Sale of own chickens		
2. Own chickens consumed		
3. Sale of own guinea fowls		
4. Own guinea fowls consumed		
5. Sale of own ducks and geese		
6. Own ducks and geese consumed		
7. Sale of own turkeys		
8. Own turkeys consumed		
9. Sale of own rabbits		
10. Own rabbits consumed		
11. Sale of own pigeons		
12. Own pigeons consumed		
13. Sale of own quails		
14. Own quails consumed		
15. Sale of own eggs		
16. Own eggs consumed		
E4. DID YOUR HOUSEHOLD FISH IN THE LAST 12 MONTHS?	YES/NO	E4a. WHAT WAS THE INCOME FROM SALES OR VALUE OF CONSUMPTION FROM FISHING IN THE LAST 12 MONTHS (IN KWACHA)
FISHERY		
Sale of fish from fishponds		
E5. DID YOUR HOUSEHOLD EARN ANY INCOME FROM ANY OTHER AGRICULTURAL ACTIVITIES IN THE LAST 12 MONTHS?	YES/NO	E5a. WHAT WAS THE INCOME FROM ANY OTHER AGRICULTURAL ACTIVITIES IN THE LAST

		12 MONTHS (IN KWACHA)
25. HINT: Other farming income (lease of tractor, agricultural land, scotch cart, lease of transport for produce, hiring out of draught animals, etc.) in the last 12 months?		
	If Yes, please specify: ...	

SECTION F: INDIVIDUAL INCOME FROM NON-AGRICULTURAL ACTIVITY – FOR ALL PERSONS AGED 5 YEARS AND ABOVE

Ask if age is 5 years or above

INTRODUCTION: I am now going to ask you about the non-agricultural income of this household in the last month.

QUESTIONS	CODE NUMBER
	KWACHA
F1. HOW MUCH INCOME DID [NAME] RECEIVE FROM [THE FOLLOWING NON-AGRICULTURAL ACTIVITIES]? Hint: Use 9999 as a code for "I don't know/I don't remember"	
F1p1. Did [NAME] receive any income from the following non-agricultural activities?	
F1a. Main non-farm business in the last one month	Integer
F1b. Other non-farm business in the last one month	Integer
F1c. Gross monthly wage - including regular allowances such as housing and transport allowances, regular overtime, retention allowance - from the main job	Integer
F1d. Nonregular allowances received last month - that is, overtime payments, subsistence allowances, bonuses, etc. - from your main job	Integer
F1e. Regular gross monthly salary/wage - including regular allowances such as housing and transport allowances, regular overtime, retention allowance - from your second job	Integer
F1p2. Did [NAME] receive any income from the following non-agricultural activities?	
F1f. Nonregular allowances received last month - that is overtime payments, subsistence allowances, bonuses, etc. - from your second job	Integer
F1g. In-kind income per month - e.g. bags of mealie meal, charcoal, etc. - from your job/s [convert to kwacha equivalent]	Integer
F1h. Rent received per month from houses, other buildings, non-agricultural equipment and non-agricultural land that you own	Integer
F1i. Remittances received last month [record only for the people who actually received it]	Integer
F1j. Pension payment received last month	Integer
F1p3. Did [NAME] receive any income from the following non-agricultural activities?	
F1k. Monthly income in form of grants that you receive per month (both cash and in-kind) [convert in-kind to its value in cash]	Integer
F1l. Borrowing last month [both cash and in-kind]	Integer
F1m. Interest on savings received in the last month	Integer
F1n. Interest or dividends on shares, securities, bonds, treasury bills, etc. that were received during the last 12 months	Integer
F1o. Income received from other sources last month	Integer
F1. HOW MUCH INCOME DID [NAME] RECEIVE FROM [THE FOLLOWING NON-AGRICULTURAL ACTIVITIES]? Hint: Use 9999 as a code for "I don't know/I don't remember"	
F1a. Main non-farm business	Integer

F1b. Other non-farm business	Integer
F1c. Gross monthly wage	Integer
F1d. Nonregular allowances received last month	Integer
F1e. Regular gross monthly salary/wage	Integer
F1f. Nonregular allowances received last month	Integer
F1g. In-kind income per month	Integer
F1h. Rent received per month from houses, other buildings, non-agricultural equipment and non-agricultural land that you own	Integer
F1i. Remittances received last month	Integer
F1j. Pension payment received last month	Integer
F1k. Monthly income in form of grants that you receive per month	Integer
F1l. Borrowing last month	Integer
F1m. Interest in savings received in the last month	Integer
F1n. Interest or dividends on shares, securities, bonds, treasury bills, etc. that were received during the last 12 months	Integer
F1o. Income received from other sources last month	Integer

SECTION G: HOUSEHOLD ASSETS

INTRODUCTION: I am now going to ask you about the household assets

QUESTIONS	CODE NUMBER
	YES/NO
G1. GENERAL ITEMS - Do you own any of the following items?	
1. Bed	
2. Mattress	
3. Mosquito net	
4. Table (dining)	
5. Lounge suite/sofa	
6. Radio/stereo	
7. Television	
8. Satellite dish/decoder (free to air)	
9. Satellite dish/decoder (DSTV)	
10. Other paid TV	
11. DVD/VCR	
12. Home theatre	
13. Landline phone	
14. Cellular phone	
15. Computer	
16. Watch	
17. Clock	
G1. HOW MANY [ITEMS] DOES YOUR HOUSEHOLD OWN? [TICK ALL THAT APPLY]	
	Integer
1. Bed	
2. Mattress	
3. Mosquito net	
4. Table (dining)	
5. Lounge suite/sofa	
6. Radio/stereo	
7. Television	
8. Satellite dish/decoder (free to air)	
9. Satellite dish/decoder (DSTV)	
10. Other paid TV	
11. DVD/VCR	
12. Home theatre	
13. Landline phone	
14. Cellular phone	
15. Computer	
16. Watch	
17. Clock	

G2. KITCHEN/HOUSEHOLD - Do you have any of the following items?	YES/NO
1. Residential building	
2. Non-residential building	
3. Brazier/mbaula	
4. Gas stove	
5. Electric stove	
6. Refrigerator	
7. Deep freezer	
8. Washing machine	
9. Dish washer	
10. Air conditioner/ventilator	
11. Electric iron	
12. Non-electric iron	
13. Private water pump	
G2-How many	Integer
1. How many residential buildings does your household own?	
2. How many non-residential buildings does your household own?	
3. How many brazier/mbaula does your household own?	
4. How many gas stoves does your household own?	
5. How many electric stoves does your household own?	
6. How many refrigerators does your household own?	
7. How many deep freezers does your household own?	
8. How many washing machines does your household own?	
9. How many dish washers does your household own?	
10. how many air conditioners/ventilators does your household own?	
11. how many electric irons does your household own?	
12. how many non-electric irons does your household own?	
13. how many private water pumps does your household own?	
G3. TOOLS & MACHINES - Do you have any of the following items?	YES/NO
1. Sewing machine	
2. Hand-powered hammer mill	
3. Machine powered grinding/hammer mill	
4. Sheller	
5. Ramp presses/oil expellers	
6. Hand saw	
7. Carpentry plane	
8. Axe	

9. Pick	
10. Hoe	
11. Hammer	
12. Shovel/spade	
13. Fishing net	
14. Hunting gun	
15. Plough	
16. Crop sprayer	
17. Knitting machine	
18. Lawn mowers	
19. Generator	
G3-How many	Integer
How many sewing machines does your household own?	
How many hand-powered hammers mill does your household own?	
How many machines powered by grinding/hammer mill does your household own?	
How many sheller does your household own?	
How many ramp presses/oil expellers does your household own?	
How many handsaws does your household own?	
How many carpentry planes does your household own?	
How many axes does your household own?	
How many picks does your household own?	
How many hoes does your household own?	
How many hammers does your household own?	
How many shovel/spades does your household own?	
How many fishing nets does your household own?	
How many hunting guns does your household own?	
How many ploughs does your household own?	
How many crop sprayers does your household own?	
How many knitting machines does your household own?	
How many lawnmowers does your household own?	
How many generators does your household own?	
G4. TRANSPORT & ANIMALS - Do you have any of the following items?	Integer
1. Small/hand-driven tractor	
2. 4-Wheel tractor	
3. Wheelbarrow	
4. Scotch cart	
5. Bicycle	
6. Motorcycle	

7. Large truck	
8. Small/pick-up truck	
9. Van/minibus	
10. Car	
11. Canoe	
12. Boat	
13. Oxen	
14. Donkey	
G4-How many	Integer
How many 4-wheel tractors does your household own?	
How many wheelbarrows does your household own?	
How many scotch carts does your household own?	
How many bicycles does your household own?	
How many motorcycles does your household own?	
How many large trucks does your household own?	
How many small/pick-up trucks does your household own?	
How many vans/minibuses does your household own?	
How many cars does your household own?	
How many canoes does your household own?	
How many boats does your household own?	
How many oxen does your household own?	
How many donkeys does your household own?	
G5-Other.	Text
Do you own any other assets in your household?	
Please, specify any other item (1)	
Please, specify any other item (2)	
Please, specify any other item (3)	
G6. What kind of dwelling does your household live in?	
Traditional hut	
Improved traditional hut	
Detached house	
Flat/apartment/multi-unit	
Semi-detached house	
Servants' quarters	
Guest wing	
Cottage	

House attached to/on top of shop etc.	
Hostel	
Non-residential buildings (e.g. school classroom, etc.)	
Unconventional (e.g. kantemba, storage container, etc.)	
Other (specify)	
G6a. How many rooms are occupied by this household excluding bathrooms and toilets? (for rural areas count the number of rooms in each hut belonging to the household collectively?)	
	Integer
G7a. What kind of building materials is/are the roof of this dwelling made of?	NUMBER
Asbestos tiles	
Other/non-asbestos tiles	
Iron sheets	
Grass/straw/thatch	
Concrete	
Other (specify)	
Not applicable	
Don't know	
G7b. What kind of building materials is/are the walls of this dwelling made of?	
Pan brick	
Concrete brick	
Mud brick	
Burnt brick	
Pole	
Pole & dagga	
Mud	
Grass/straw	
Iron sheets	
Steel	
Hardboard	
A mixture of hardboard, tin sheet, plastic, etc.	
Other (specify)	
Not applicable	
Don't Know	
G7c. What kind of building materials is/are the floor of this dwelling made of?	
	Concrete only

Covered concrete	
Mud	
Wood only	
Other (specify)	
I don't know	
Nothing/ground	
G8. What is the main source of water supply for this household?	
Directly from river/lake/stream/dam	
Rainwater	
Unprotected well	
Protected well	
Borehole	
Unprotected spring	
Protected spring	
Public tap	
Own tap	
Other tap (e.g. from nearby building)	
Handpump (public)	
Water kiosk	
Bought from another vendor	
Other (specify)	
G9. How far is this source of water from this house? [if less than one kilometre enters "0"]	Integer
G10. What is the main source of drinking water for this household?	
Directly from river/lake/stream/dam	
Rainwater	
Unprotected well	
Protected well	
Borehole	
Unprotected spring	
Protected spring	
Public tap	
Own tap	
Other tap (e.g. from nearby building)	
Handpump (public)	
Water kiosk	
Bought from another vendor	
Bottled water	
Other (specify)	

G11. Is your house connected to electricity?	YES/NO
Yes	
No	
G12. What is the main type of energy used for lighting in your household?	
Kerosene/paraffin	
Electricity	
Solar panel	
Candle	
Diesel	
Open fire	
Torch	
None	
Other (specify)	
G13. What is the main type of energy that your household uses for cooking?	
Collected firewood	
Purchased firewood	
Charcoal own produced	
Charcoal purchased	
Coal	
Kerosene/paraffin	
Gas	
Electricity	
Solar	
Crop/livestock residues	
Other (specify)	
G14. What is the main type of toilet facility for this household?	
Own flush toilet inside the household	
Own flush toilet outside the household	
Own pit latrine with slab	
Communal pit latrine with slab	
Neighbour's/another household's pit latrine with slab	
Own pit latrine without slab	
Communal pit latrine without slab	
Neighbour's/another household's pit latrine without slab	
Bucket/another container	
Aqua privy	

None	
Other (specify)	
G15. What is the main method of garbage disposal that this household uses?	
Refuse collected	
Pit	
Dumping	
Burning	
Others	

SECTION H: AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION: I am now going to ask you about the household agricultural production

QUESTIONS	CODE NUMBER	
PRODUCTION OF AGRICULTURAL FOOD CROPS		
H1. Did any member of this household grow - or anybody grow on behalf of any household member - any food crops in the last agricultural season? (In the last 12 months)		
1. Yes		
2. No [skip to H7]		
H2. What food crops have been grown by any member of this household - or by anybody else on behalf of any member of this household - during the last agricultural season?	Tick all that apply	
<i>Ask if H1 = Yes</i>		
A. Local maize		
B. Hybrid maize		
C. Cassava (flour)		
D. Millet (threshed)		
E. Sorghum		
F. Rice (paddy)		
G. Mixed beans		
H. Soya beans		
I. Sweet potatoes		
J. Irish potatoes		
K. Vegetables		
L. Groundnuts (shelled)		
M. Impwa		
N. Eggplant		
O. Okra		
H3. What was the area planted under ...? in the last agricultural season		
<i>In the last 12 months</i>	AREA	UNIT
A. Local maize		1. Lima
B. Hybrid maize		2. Acre
C. Cassava (flour)		3. Hectare
D. Millet (threshed)		
E. Sorghum		
F. Rice (paddy)		
G. Mixed beans		
H. Soya beans		
I. Sweet potatoes		

J. Irish potatoes		
K. Vegetables		
L. Groundnuts (shelled)		
M. Impwa		
N. Eggplant		
O. Okra		
H4. From what you planted, what quantity of ... did all the members of the household harvest in the last agricultural season? [In KG]	QUANTITY	
A. Local maize	1. Kg	
B. Hybrid maize	2. 20 ltr. Tin	
C. Cassava (flour)	3. 25 kg bag	
D. Millet (threshed)	4. 50 kg bag	
E. Sorghum	5. 90 kg bag	
F. Rice (paddy)		
G. Mixed beans		
H. Soya beans		
I. Sweet potatoes		
J. Irish potatoes		
K. Vegetables		
L. Groundnuts (shelled)		
M. Impwa		
N. Eggplant		
O. Okra		
H5. What quantity of ... did the household sell in the last agricultural season? [In KG]	QUANTITY	
A. Local maize		
B. Hybrid maize		
C. Cassava (flour)		
D. Millet (threshed)		
E. Sorghum		
F. Rice (paddy)		
G. Mixed beans		
H. Soya beans		
I. Sweet potatoes		
J. Irish potatoes		
K. Vegetables		
L. Groundnuts (shelled)		
M. Impwa		
N. Eggplant		

O. Okra		
H6. How much was received from the sale of...?	TOTAL VALUE IN KWACHA	
A. Hybrid maize		
B. Local maize		
C. Cassava (flour)		
D. Millet (threshed)		
E. Sorghum		
F. Rice (paddy)		
G. Mixed beans		
H. Soya beans		
I. Sweet potatoes		
J. Irish potatoes		
K. Vegetables		
L. Groundnuts (shelled)		
M. Impwa		
N. Eggplant		
O. Okra		
PRODUCTION OF AGRICULTURAL NON-FOOD CROPS		
H7. Did any member of this household grow or anybody grow on behalf of any member of this household any non- food crops in the last agricultural season, that is, in the last 12 months?	YES....1 NO.....2 [IF ALL ARE "NO", SKIP TO S8Q10]	
A. Cotton		
B. Tobacco		
C. Sunflower		
D. Paprika		
E. Flowers		
H8. What was the area planted for this crop?		LIMA.....1 ACRE.....2 HECTARE.....3
	AREA	UNIT
A. Cotton		
B. Tobacco		
C. Sunflower		
D. Paprika		
E. Flowers		
H9. From what was planted, what quantity of ... was harvested? [In KG]		

	QUANTITY
A. Cotton	
B. Tobacco	
C. Sunflower	
D. Paprika	
E. Flowers	
LIVESTOCK/POULTRY OWNERSHIP	
H10. Does any member of this household own any.....?	YES....1 NO.....2 [IF ALL ARE "NO" SKIP TO S8Q12]
A. Cattle	
B. Goats	
C. Pigs	
D. Sheep	
H10a. Number of [.] owned [should be greater than "0" for each expense incurred]	
A. Cattle	Integer
B. Goats	Integer
C. Pigs	Integer
D. Sheep	Integer
H11. Does any member of this household own any.....?	YES....1 NO.....2 [IF ALL ARE "NO" SKIP TO S8Q14]
A. Chickens	
B. Ducks & geese	
C. Guinea fowls	
D. Any other poultry (e.g. turkey, rabbits, pigeons, quails)	
H11a. Number of [.] owned	
A. Chickens	Integer
B. Ducks & geese	Integer
C. Guinea fowls	Integer
D. Any other poultry (e.g. turkey, rabbits, pigeons, quails)	Integer
FISH FARMING	
H12. Is any member of this household engaged in fish farming?	
Yes	1

No [skip to S8Q16]	2
H12a. Quantity of fish harvested in the last 12 months [Should be greater than 0]	Kilograms
CROP PRODUCTION	
<u>We are trying to understand the costs and expenses incurred during the last agriculture season, that is, in the last 12 months for the production of crops</u>	
H13a. Did you use /incur any of the following during the last agriculture season?	YES....1 NO.....2 [IF ALL ARE "NO" SKIP TO S8Q18]
A. Fertilizer (inorganic)	
B. Organic fertilizer	
C. Insecticides	
D. Herbicides	
E. Any crop storage facility	
F. Purchased seed, seedlings	
G. Irrigation equipment	
H. Bags, containers, strings	
I. Petrol/diesel/oil	
H13b. Did you use /incur during the last agriculture season?	YES....1 NO.....2 [IF ALL ARE "NO" SKIP TO S8Q18]
A. Fertilizer (inorganic)	
B. Organic fertilizer	
C. Insecticides	
D. Herbicides	
E. Any crop storage facility	
F. Purchased seed, seedlings etc.	
G. Irrigation equipment	
H. Bags, containers, strings	
I. Petrol/diesel/oil	

J. Costs on repairs/maintenance of agricultural equipment including purchase of spare parts	
K. Hired labour	
L. Any transport costs	
M. Hired animals	
N. Hired equipment	
O. Local hand tools	
P. Imported hand tools	
Q. Any other crop production related costs	
H13c. How much was spent in cash and in kind on..... during the last agriculture season? [CONVERT IN KIND TO CASH EQUIVALENT] [should be greater than "0" for each expense incurred]	AMOUNT IN KWACHA [code "9999" for don't know / don't remember]
A. Fertilizer (inorganic)	
B. Organic fertilizer	
C. Insecticides	
D. Herbicides	
E. Any crop storage facility	
F. Purchased seed, seedlings etc.	
G. Irrigation equipment	
H. Bags, containers, strings	
I. Petrol/diesel/oil	
J. Costs on repairs/maintenance of agricultural equipment including purchase of spare parts	
K. Hired labour	
L. Any transport costs	
M. Hired animals	
N. Hired equipment	
O. Local hand tools	
P. Imported hand tools	
Q. Any other crop production related costs	
LIVESTOCK PRODUCTION	
<u>We are trying to understand the costs and expenses incurred during the last agriculture season, that is, in the last 12 months for the production of livestock</u>	
H14. Which of the following did you use/pay for the production of livestock during the last agriculture season?	YES....1 NO.....2 [IF ALL ARE "NO" SKIP TO S8Q20]
A. Animal feed including salt	
B. Veterinary services including vaccination and medicine	

C. Any hired labour	
D. Maintenance of pens, stables	
E. Transport	
F. Commission on sale of animals	
G. Compensation for damage caused by animals	
H. Any other livestock production related costs	
H14a. How much was spent in cash and in kind on..... during the last agriculture season? [CONVERT IN KIND TO CASH EQUIVALENT]	AMOUNT IN KWACHA [code "9999" for don't know / don't remember]
A. Animal feed including salt	
B. Veterinary services including vaccination and medicine	
C. Any hired labour	
D. Maintenance of pens, stables	
E. Transport	
F. Commission on sale of animals	
G. Compensation for damage caused by animals	
H. Any other livestock production related costs	
POULTRY PRODUCTION	
<u>We are trying to understand the costs and expenses incurred during the last agriculture season, that is, in the last 12 months for the production of poultry</u>	
H15. Which of the following did you use/pay for the production of poultry during the last agriculture season?	YES....1 NO.....2 [IF ALL ARE "NO" SKIP TO S8Q22]
A. Animal feed including salt	
B. Veterinary services including vaccination and medicine	
C. Any hired labour	
D. Maintenance of pens, stables	
E. Transport	
F. Commission on sale of animals	
G. Compensation for damage caused by animals	
H. Any other livestock production related costs	
H15a. How much was spent in cash and in kind on..... during the last agriculture season? [CONVERT IN KIND TO CASH EQUIVALENT] [should be greater than "0" for each expense incurred]	AMOUNT IN KWACHA [code "9999" for don't know / don't remember]
A. Animal feed including salt	

B. Veterinary services including vaccination and medicine	
C. Any hired labour	
D. Maintenance of pens, stables	
E. Transport	
F. Commission on sale of animals	
G. Compensation for damage caused by animals	
H. Any other livestock production related costs	
FISH FARMING	
<u>We are trying to understand the costs and expenses incurred during the last agriculture season, that is, in the last 12 months for the production of fish</u>	
H16. Which of the following did you use/pay for the production of fish during the last agriculture season?	YES....1 NO.....2 [IF ALL ARE "NO" SKIP TO S9Q1]
A. Purchase of fingerlings	
B. Feed	
C. Hired labour	
D. Repairs and maintenance of fishponds	
E. Repairs and maintenance of fishpond related equipment	
F. Medicines for fish	
G. Transport costs	
H. Hand tools	
I. Other fish farming production related costs	
H16a. How much was spent in cash and in kind on..... during the last agriculture season? [CONVERT IN KIND TO CASH EQUIVALENT] [should be greater than "0" for each expense incurred]	AMOUNT IN KWACHA [code "9999" for don't know / don't remember]
A. Purchase of fingerlings	
B. Feed	
C. Hired labour	
D. Repairs and maintenance of fishponds	
E. Repairs and maintenance of fishpond related equipment	
F. Medicines for fish	
G. Transport costs	
H. Hand tools	
I. Other fish farming production related costs	

SECTION I: CLIMATE RESILIENCE

INTRODUCTION: I am now going to ask you about the household climate perception, knowledge, and adaptations

QUESTIONS	CODE NUMBER				
PERCEPTIONS ON EXPERIENCING CLIMATE CHANGE					
I1. How have you experienced a change in the following climate events over the last 20 Years? 1 = Increased 2 = No Change 3 = Decreased 4 = Don't Know	1 digit				
Temperature					
Rainfall					
Occurrence of drought					
Occurrence of flood					
Occurrence of severe storms					
Extremely hot days					
Extremely cold nights					
Occurrence of soil erosion					
Short winter season					
Long summer season					
Unpredictable rainfall					
Other (specify)					
I2-17. Have the following climate risks and events occurred in past 5 years? 1 = Yes 2 = No 99 = I don't know/I don't remember	1 = Yes 2 = No				
	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Droughts					
Flood					
Soil erosion					
Severe storms					
Extreme hot days					
Extreme cold nights					
Other (specify)					
<i>Skip to SECTION J QUESTION 1 if the respondent did not report any weather events and climate risks in past five years (i.e. if all of them are No)</i>					

<p>I3. How many times did [EVENT] happen in past 12 months? (For comparison with LCMS) [Question is asked only if mentioned in I2_17] Enter number of events [Value should be greater than 0] <i>If I2at 2017 Droughts= Yes</i></p>	<p>1 digit</p>
Droughts	
Flood	
<p>I4. How would you rate the severity (seriousness) of the following climate risks and events?</p>	<p>1 digit 1 = Negligible; 2 = Minor; 3 = Moderate; 4 = Severe; 5 = Extremely severe; 6 = I have never experienced any of some</p>
Droughts	
Flood	
Soil erosion	
Severe storms	
Extreme hot days	
Extreme cold nights	
Other (specify)	
<p>I5. Have the below climate events and risks been happening more FREQUENTLY in the past 5 years compared to the past?</p>	<p>1 digit 1 = More; 2 = Less; 3 = About the same</p>
Droughts	
Flood	
Soil erosion	
Severe storms	
Extremely hot days	
Extremely cold nights	
Other (specify)	
<p>I6. Has [climate risk] been happening more severely in the past 5 years compared to the past?</p>	<p>1 digit 1 = More 2 = Less 3 = About the same</p>
Droughts	
Flood	

Soil erosion	
Severe storms	
Extremely hot days	
Extremely cold nights	
Other (specify)	
IMPACT OF CLIMATE RISK	
I7. Considering all the weather events and climate risks you have experienced, how is it affecting your life and ability to earn a living at the present time?	1 digit
Not at all	1
A little	2
Somewhat but not the key risk	3
A lot (a key risk)	4
Completely (the primary risk)	5
I8. How would you rate the economic impact (loss of income) of the weather events and climate risks you have experienced on you and your family (household)?	1 digit
No impact	1
Little impact	2
Bad impact	3
Very bad impact	4
Devastating impact	5
I9. Have you consistently (regularly) lost your ability to earn income as a result of the weather events and climate risks you have experienced?	1 digit
No	1
A little	2
Somewhat	3
Often	4
Most of the time	5
I10. How would you rate the effect often weather events and climate risks you have experienced on your crop production?	1 digit
No impact	1
Little impact	2
Bad impact	3
Very bad impact	4
Devastating impact	5

I11. Has any farmland become unusable for farming as a result of often weather events and climate risks you have experienced?	1 digit		
No	1		
A little	2		
Somewhat	3		
A lot	4		
Most	5		
I12. Approximately, how much did you lose in crop production (in ZMK) as a result of the weather events and climate risks you have experienced in past 12 months? [Only for selected in H2]			
	1 digit	Number of units	Total value
A. Local maize	1		
B. Hybrid maize	2		
C. Cassava (flour)	3		
D. Millet (threshed)	4		
E. Sorghum	5		
F. Rice (paddy)	6		
G. Mixed beans	7		
H. Soya beans	8		
I. Sweet potatoes	9		
J. Irish potatoes	10		
K. Groundnuts (shelled)	11		
I13. How would you rate the effect of the weather events and climate risks you have experienced on your livestock? (Did you have to sell any livestock, or did they die?)	1 digit		
No impact	1		
Little impact	2		
Bad impact	3		
Very bad impact	4		
Devastating impact	5		
I14. Did any of your livestock or animals die as a result of the weather events and climate risks you have experienced in past five years?	1 digit		
Yes	1		
No [skip to I.17]	2		
<i>Ask if I14 = 1</i>			

I15. How many animals and livestock died as a result of the weather events and climate risks you have experienced in past five years?	QUANTITY	
a. Cattle		
b. Goats and sheep		
c. Pigs		
d. Horses and donkeys		
e. Poultry		
f. Others, specify		
I16. Approximately, how much did you lose in animals and livestock (in ZMK) as a result of the weather events and climate risks in the last year?	1 digit	Total Value
a. Cattle	Integer	
b. Goats and sheep	Integer	
c. Pigs	Integer	
d. Horses and donkeys	Integer	
e. Poultry	Integer	
f. Others, specify	Integer	
I17. Have the weather events and climate risks that we have discussed caused you to be deprived of food (to be hungry) in the past five years?		
Yes		
No >> [skip to I19]		
I18. In the course of the last 12 months, how long were you without food (hungry) because of the weather events and climate risks?	1 digit	
Never/0 days	0	
A few days	1	
A week	2	
A few weeks	3	
A month	4	
More than a month	5	
More than 3 months	6	
More than 5 months	7	
RESPONDING TO CLIMATE RISK		
I19. After a weather event/ a climate risk occurred, did you make any changes to the way you live or earn a living in order to prevent such negative impacts to happen in the future?	1 digit	
No change at all	1	

Changed slightly	2
Changed a lot	3
Changed completely	4
<i>Ask If H1 = 1 or H7num >0</i>	
I20. How important are the below adaptative strategies to your agricultural enterprise [only if H2 or H7 is filled]	1 = High 2 = Medium 3 = Low 4 = No
Increased use of irrigation	
Practicing crop diversification	
Integrated farming system	
Use of drought tolerant varieties	
Use of salinity tolerant varieties	
Practicing crop rotation	
Cultivating short duration crops	
Practicing intercropping	
Find off-farm job	
Moved to non-farm activities	
Agro-forestry	
Soil conservations techniques	
Zero tillage	
Crop insurance	
<i>Ask If H1 = 1 or H7num >0</i>	
I21. How important are the below constraint with regard to the adoption of coping strategies? [only if H2 or H7 is filled]	1 = High 2 = Medium 3 = Low 4 = No
Lack of available water (both irrigation and drinking)	
Shortage of cultivable land	
Unpredicted weather	
Lack of credit/money	
Lack of market access	
Lack of farm animals	
Shortage of farm inputs	
Lack of information	
Poor soil fertility	
Insecure property rights	
Other (specify)	
PRECAUTION AND MITIGATION	

I22. How would you rate your ability to take precautions (be prepared) against the negative effects of climate risks?	1 digit
Completely unprepared	1
Unprepared	2
Slightly prepared	3
Fairly prepared	4
Very prepared	5
I23. Which of the following precautions have you ever taken against the effects of climate risks? [Tick all that apply]	1 digit
Plant in different fields	1
Plant different crops	2
Move livestock to higher ground	3
Seek advice from camp officer	4
Store dry food	5
Save money for crisis period	6
Improve the structure of the house	7
None	
Other (specify)	8
I24. What do you think would help improve the negative effects that climate risk has on you? (Please check all that apply)	1 digit
Weather forecast	1
Access to information	2
Access to microfinance/loans	3
Improved road access	4
Better water management (dams)	5
Technical knowledge	6
Financial support	7
None	
Others (specify)	8
I25. Do you have any form of insurance that provides you with financial protection in case of negative effects of climate risk?	
Yes	
No >> skip to I27	
I26. Where does this insurance come from? (Please check all that apply)	1 digit
Government	1

Private	2
NGO	3
Others (specify)	98
I27. Do you ever use any of the following methods to enhance (improve) your farming (Please check all that apply)	1 digit
Fertiliser or manure	1
Any chemicals (pesticides/herbicides)	2
Irrigation for watering	3
Conservation farming	4
Early maturing varieties	5
Different crop varieties	6
Planting in different locations	7
I don't use any methods to enhance (improve) my farming	99
Other (please specify)	98
EARLY WARNING AND PREPARATION	
I28. Which of the following types of information about climate risks do you receive? (Please check all that apply)	1 digit
Radio broadcasts about climate/weather	1
Television updates about climate/weather	2
Text (SMS) messages about climate/weather	3
Message from agricultural officer/other government official	4
Message from NGO representative	5
I don't receive any type of information about climate risks	99
Other (specify)	98
I29. In general, how informed are you of climate risks before they affect you or your community?	1 digit
Not informed	1
Slightly informed	2
Fairly informed	3
Very informed	4
Completely informed	5
I30. Are you able to predict when these climate risks will occur?	1 digit
Yes	1
No	2
I31. Are there methods or systems of communication with other community members, or other communities, about when such a climate risk is coming?	1 digit

Yes	1
No	2

SECTION 10: PPCR PROJECTS

INTRODUCTION: I am now going to ask you about the PPCR projects.

QUESTIONS	CODE NUMBER
AWARENESS OF PPCR PROJECTS	
<p><i>PPCR projects are supported by the World Bank and intended to improve agricultural household's resilience to climate change. Specific activities include the followings:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Diversification of agricultural and livestock practices and livelihood opportunities into sustainable activities that are not climate sensitive, including bee-keeping, crafts using local non-timber materials, and processing aquaculture</i> - <i>Moving households to less climate sensitive locations</i> - <i>Building infrastructure for water management to reduce effects of flooding</i> - <i>Rehabilitation and management of canals for improvement of drainage and water storage to overcome shorter growing seasons and allow for early planting and full maturation</i> - <i>At ward level, building schools, health clinics and halls, which may also act as flood shelters and facilitation</i> - <i>Equipping local livestock Para-vet centers for vaccination and disease control</i> 	
J1. Are/were you a beneficiary of the PPCR projects?	
Yes	1
No [skip to J3]	2
<i>Ask If J1 = 1</i>	
J2. If Yes, what is the status of the PPCR projects of which you are/were a beneficiary?	
Ongoing	1
Completed and functional	2
Completed with some challenges	3
Terminated	4
I don't know	5
<i>Ask to all respondents</i>	
J3. Do you know if there are any PPCR projects located in the same ward, district or province as your house?	[Multiple choice]
In ward	1
In district	2
In province	3
Outside province	4
Don't know	5
<i>If J1 = No</i>	
J3a. Did you receive any benefits from the PPCR projects?	1. Yes; 2. No
<i>Hint: (Benefits do not have to be monetary. For example, you might receive benefit from infrastructure built by the project and useful information from the PPCR beneficiaries etc.)</i>	

BENEFICIARIES OF PPCR PROJECTS	
<i>If J1 = Yes or J3a = Yes</i>	
J4. What type of projects are/were you a beneficiary of or receive benefits from the projects?	[Multiple choice]
Infrastructure	1
Construction of water resource supply	2
Crop production	3
Livestock	4
Poultry	5
Fish farming	6
Farmer group	7

TYPE OF PPCR PROJECTS					
<i>If J1 = No</i>			<i>If J5c = No</i>	<i>SKIP if J2=2 or J2=3 or J2=4</i>	<i>ONLY if J2=2 or J2=3 or J2=4</i>
J5a. Which of the following adaptative strategies are encouraged by the PPCR project(s), which you are/were a beneficiary of or receive benefits from (even if indirect benefits)?? [Tick all that apply]	J5b. Were you applying these adaptative strategies before the PPCR project?	J5c. Are/were you applying these adaptative strategies during the PPCR project implementation?	J5ca. Why aren't/weren't you applying these adaptative strategies during the PPCR project implementation	J5d. Do you think you will apply these strategies after the PPCR project ends?	J5e. Have you applied these strategies since the project ended?
1 = Yes 2 = No	1 = Yes 2 = No	1 = Yes 2 = No		1 = Yes 2 = No	1 = Yes 2 = No
Adaptation of crops and crop management					
Encourage introduction of new crops that require less water					
Encourage introduction of new crops that are adapted to higher temperatures					
Encourage changes in sowing dates					
Provide shade and drinking water for animals at pasture					
Develop breeds or change to breeds adapted to changed conditions, especially drought and heat-resistant varieties					
Restoring natural features such as hedgerows to help reduce erosion					
Develop farming practices that minimize susceptibility to new pests and diseases					
Increase ground cover, by changing field design e.g. to expanded field margins					
Enhancing the efficiency of fertilizer use					
Developing land management practices to adapt to changes in soil properties					
Maximising effectiveness of labour and machinery					

TYPE OF PPCR PROJECTS					
<i>If J1 = No</i>			<i>If J5c = No</i>	<i>SKIP if J2=2 or J2=3 or J2=4</i>	<i>ONLY if J2=2 or J2=3 or J2=4</i>
J5a. Which of the following adaptative strategies are encouraged by the PPCR project(s), which you are/were a beneficiary of or receive benefits from (even if indirect benefits)?? [Tick all that apply]	J5b. Were you applying these adaptative strategies before the PPCR project?	J5c. Are/were you applying these adaptative strategies during the PPCR project implementation?	J5ca. Why aren't/weren't you applying these adaptative strategies during the PPCR project implementation	J5d. Do you think you will apply these strategies after the PPCR project ends?	J5e. Have you applied these strategies since the project ended?
1 = Yes 2 = No	1 = Yes 2 = No	1 = Yes 2 = No		1 = Yes 2 = No	1 = Yes 2 = No
Facilitate the transfer of technologies from relevant climatic zones					
Adaptation of agricultural water management					
Adopt suitable upland farm or land management practices so that upland areas are used to slow run off and reduce peak water flows					
Adopt measures to reduce the impacts of extreme precipitation events					
Encourage introduction of new management techniques e.g. requiring less water					
Introduce measures to secure safety of livestock during extreme flooding events					
Alter conservation practices for dry summers					
Adopt more effective use of irrigation					
Increase in irrigation area and or water volume					
Adopt water re-use technology					
Controlling, monitoring, and information systems					

TYPE OF PPCR PROJECTS					
<i>If J1 = No</i>			<i>If J5c = No</i>	<i>SKIP if J2=2 or J2=3 or J2=4</i>	<i>ONLY if J2=2 or J2=3 or J2=4</i>
J5a. Which of the following adaptative strategies are encouraged by the PPCR project(s), which you are/were a beneficiary of or receive benefits from (even if indirect benefits)?? [Tick all that apply]	J5b. Were you applying these adaptative strategies before the PPCR project?	J5c. Are/were you applying these adaptative strategies during the PPCR project implementation?	J5ca. Why aren't/weren't you applying these adaptative strategies during the PPCR project implementation	J5d. Do you think you will apply these strategies after the PPCR project ends?	J5e. Have you applied these strategies since the project ended?
1 = Yes 2 = No	1 = Yes 2 = No	1 = Yes 2 = No		1 = Yes 2 = No	1 = Yes 2 = No
Monitoring the changes on biodiversity that may occur due to changes in agricultural crops (for example, changes in rice fields modify the habitats of many bird species)					
Monitoring new pests and diseases					
Monitoring changes in soil properties					
Information systems to raise awareness of the changes and possible risks and opportunities					
Structural and financial adaptation					
Permanent changes in farm structure, such as buildings, irrigation systems, heating or cooling structure					
Establishing business plans with regular reviews to ensure effective responses to climatic events					
Planning for capital investment to adapt to climate change					
Development of a common strategy for adaptation to climate change between the farming sectors and the insurance community					

SECTION K: HOUSEHOLD ACCESS TO FACILITIES

INTRODUCTION: I am now going to ask you about the household access to facilities.

QUESTIONS	CODE NUMBER
K1. Do you use the following? [READ OUT FACILITIES]	YES=1, NO=2
1. Food market	
2. Hammer mill	
3. Input market	
4. Bank	
5. Internet cafe	
K2. How far is your household's dwelling to the nearest [FACILITY] in kilometres? [Read out facilities. If less than a kilometre enters 0. If don't know enter 99.]	KILOMETERS
1. Food market	
2. Hammer mill	
3. Input market	
4. Bank	
5. Internet cafe	

SECTION L: DEVELOPMENTAL ISSUES

INTRODUCTION: I am now going to ask you about the household developmental issues

QUESTIONS	CODE NUMBER
L1a. Have the following projects or changes occurred in your community in the last 12 months?	YES=1, NO=2, Don't Know=3
Building of new tarred road?	
Extension of existing tarred road?	
Rehabilitation or resurfacing of existing tarred road?	
Building a new gravel road?	
Rehabilitation or grading or resurfacing or extension of existing gravel road?	
Digging off well?	
Sinking of borehole?	
L1b. Have the following projects or changes occurred in your community in the last 12 months?	
Piping of water?	
Water supply rehabilitated or improved?	
Provision of hammermills?	
Transport services provided or improved?	
Agricultural inputs provided on credit?	
Agricultural inputs provided on a subsidized basis?	
Buyers of agricultural produce available or improved?	
L1c. Have the following projects or changes occurred in your community in the last 12 months?	
Credit facility now being provided	
More employment opportunities available	
Agricultural extension service available or improved?	
Veterinary services now provided or improved?	
Agricultural inputs now more readily available?	
Provision of mobile phone network?	
L2. To what extent has this activity/project improved the way you live?	EXTREMELY=1 MODERATELY=2 LITTLE=3 NO EFFECT=4 NOT APPLICABLE=5
Building of new tarred road?	
Extension of existing tarred road?	
Rehabilitation or resurfacing of existing tarred road?	

Building a new gravel road?	
Rehabilitation or grading or resurfacing or extension of existing gravel road?	
Digging off well?	
Sinking of borehole?	
Piping of water?	
Water supply rehabilitated or improved?	
Provision of hammermill/s?	
Transport services provided or improved?	
Agricultural inputs provided on credit?	
Agricultural inputs provided on a subsidized basis?	
Buyers of agricultural produce available or improved?	
Credit facility now being provided	
More employment opportunities available	
Agricultural extension service available or improved?	
Veterinary services now provided or improved?	
Agricultural inputs now more readily available?	
Provision of mobile phone network?	